

Studies in the Cyclo-octane Series. Part I. Synthesis of Cyclo-octyl Acetic Acid, α -Substituted Acetic Acids and *d*- and *l*-form of Cyclo-octyl Succinic Acids

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Ethyl cyclo-octylidene- α -cyanoacetate, obtained by condensing cyclo-octanone with ethyl cyanoacetate was reduced with aluminium amalgam; hydrolysis of the reduced ester gave cyclo-octyl malonic acid which on pyrolysis yielded cyclo-octyl acetic acid.

Ethyl cyclo-octyl-cyanoacetate was condensed with alkyl and aryl halide in presence of sodium ethoxide where respective ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -substituted- α -cyanoacetates were obtained and these on subsequent hydrolysis furnished the corresponding cyclo-octyl- α -substituted acetic acids.

Condensation of the above reduced ester with ethyl bromoacetate and subsequent hydrolysis of the diethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyano succinate gave dicyclo-octyl succinic acid which was resolved into its *d*- and *l*-forms.

Considerable interest attaches to the preparation of cycloalkane aliphatic acids, their esters with amino alcohols, steroidal alcohols and a few other derivatives since these are found to exhibit antibacterial activity. A number of cycloalkylbarbituric acids¹ prepared from cycloalkyl malonic acids have also been reported as sedatives and hypnotics².

During the course of the synthesis of some cyclic compounds Vogel had prepared cyclopentylmalonic acid and also studied the effect of the substituents on the course of reduction of the intermediate α - β -unsaturated esters. He observed that the yield of the bimolecular product was greater in the cycloheptane than in the cyclohexane compounds, which would appear to provide evidence for the multiplanar configuration of the seven membered ring, a result in accord with the conclusion arrived at by other groups of workers³⁻⁶. Cyclopentyl acetic acid⁸ was first prepared by heating cyclopentyl malonic acid and later by other methods⁹⁻¹². A large number of cyclopentane and cyclohexane acids¹³⁻¹⁵ analogous to chaulmoogric and hydnoarpic acids have been prepared and

1. Shonle, Keltch & Swanson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2440.
2. Fischer & Dilthey, *Ann.*, 1904, 335, 334.
3. Vogel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2010.
4. Baker & Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 122.
5. Dickens, Horton & Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1830.
6. Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1678.
7. Meerwein, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1922, 104, 161.
8. Yerwey, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1996.
9. Wallach, *Ann.*, 1907, 353, 304.
10. Huckel, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1935, 142, (ii), 205.
11. Astwood, Bisell & Hughes, *Endocrinology*, 1945, 37, 560.
12. Doering & Knox, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 4947.
13. Mayer, Burger & Matanscheck, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1961, 14, 261.
14. Adams *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 1080; 1927, 49, 2934, 2940; 1928, 50, 1475, 1503; 1932, 54, 548.
15. Adams *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2727; 1926, 48, 1074, 1089, 2393; 1927, 49, 2664.

examined 'in vitro' for their antibacterial activity against *B. Leprae* and some of these were found to be highly bactericidal.

Quite a few disubstituted acetic acids¹⁶ of the types (I and II; R=H) have been synthesised and the sodium salts of these acids when refluxed with diethylaminoethyl chloride gave diethylaminoethyl esters of the type I and II; R₁ = -COO.CH₂.CH₂.N.Et₂.

Fig 1

All these esters were found to possess some degree of antispasmodic activity.

The preparation of cyclohexyl malonic¹⁷ and acetic acids^{18,19} has also been reported. The synthesis of a number of cyclohexyl and Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl malonates has been described²⁰ and these on saponification yield the disubstituted acetic acids (III and IV; R₁=H); some acids of this type have also been synthesised by Desai and Saharia²¹. These acids when condensed with diethylaminoethyl alcohol gave the basic esters (III and IV; R₁=COO.CH₂.CH₂.N.Et₂) which were found to possess antispasmodic activity.

A number of cyclohexane aliphatic acids²² have also been tested for their mosquito repellent effect and it was observed that the effectiveness increased with the increase in the number of carbon atoms in the structural side chain with a maximum of three carbon atoms.

Fig. 2

Cycloheptyl malonic and cycloheptyl acetic acids^{23,24} have also been reported and more

16. Moffett, Hart & Hoehn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1849.
17. Heir & Adams, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 2385.
18. Ipatiev & Raskvajov, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 306.
19. Adams & Marshall, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1970.
20. Gutt, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2067.
21. Hope & Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1363.
22. Moffett, Hart & Hoehn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1854.
23. Desai & Saharia, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1940, 9, 107.
24. Gozick, Hall, Smith & Gilbert, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1957, 50, 175.
25. Kon *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1435.
26. Wallach, *Ann.*, 1907, 359, 301.

recently the latter acid and other substituted acetic acids of the type V have been reported by Saharia and Tyagi²⁷.

Cyclo-octyl malonic acid²⁸ has been condensed with urea and thiourea with the idea of evaluating the pharmacological properties of these barbiturates. This acid on pyrolysis furnished cyclo-octyl acetic acid²⁹ which was earlier synthesised by Ruzicka and Bockenoogen³⁰.

Cyclopentyl succinic acid^{31,32} has been prepared and resolved by Ranganathan³¹; the imides of cyclopentyl and cyclopentenyl succinic acids were found to be sedatives and anticonvulsants.

Cyclohexyl succinic acid has also been reported³³⁻³⁵ in literature. Sukh Dev has described the synthesis of cycloheptyl succinic acid³⁶ which has also been recently prepared by Saharia *et al.*, employing a different route with a view to study the stereochemistry of this acid (Private communication).

In view of the importance of these acids and their derivatives as therapeutic agents, and study of the chemistry of the cyclo-octane ring, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some mono- and di-carboxylic acids of cyclo-octane. Another idea of this work was to determine the influence of this ring on the antibacterial properties of these acids and compare with their lower analogues and also investigate the stereochemistry of cyclo-octyl succinic acid.

Cyclo-Octanone(VI) was condensed with ethylcyanoacetate to form ethyl cyclo-octylidene - α -cyanoacetate (VII) which on reduction with aluminium amalgam and moist ether gave ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyanoacetate(VIII); a glassy solid, believed to be a dimer, was also obtained which could not be purified.

Fig. 3

This ester on alkaline hydrolysis gave cyclo-octyl malonic acid (IX), m.p. 134-5° (decomp); Jones and Withey (loc. cit) report its m.p. 123-4°.

27. Saharia & Tyagi, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 504.
28. Jones & Withey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3490.
29. Blicke & Johnson, *J. Amer. Pharm. Soc., Sci. Ed.*, 1956, 45, 443.
30. Ruzicka & Bockenoogen, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1931, 14, 1319.
31. Ranganathan, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 107.
32. C.A., 51, 15596a; Brit. 7681, 840, Feb. 28, 1957.
33. Desai and Saharia, *Brit. Chem. Abstr.*, A II, 1941, 100.
34. Mathieson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3251.
35. Fredga & Matell, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belges*, 1953, 62, 47.
36. Sukh Dev, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 32, 255.

This acid on pyrolysis furnished cyclo-octyl acetic acid (XI; R=H), amide of which had m.p. identical with that reported by Ruzicka *et al.*, (*loc. cit.*).

The ester (VIII) was later condensed with methyl iodide, ethyl bromide, allyl iodide, benzyl chloride and ethyl bromoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide to give the respective cyanoesters of the type X, which on hydrolysis yielded the corresponding acids of the type XI.

Cyclo-octyl succinic acid (XI; R=—CH₂COOH) has been resolved into its enantiomorphs with brucine; an interesting observation in regard to the enantiomorphs was that each had a lower melting point than the racemate like the cyclohexane analogue (Fredga and Matell, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Cyclo-octyl malonic acid: Ethyl cyclo-octylidene- α -cyanoacetate (16 g) (b.p. 148-9°/2 mm n_D^{20} 1.5048 prepared by condensing cyclo-octanone with ethyl cyanoacetate by Cope's method in 75% yield) was reduced with aluminium amalgam prepared from good grade aluminium foil (20 g) in ether solution and worked up in the usual manner. Pure ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyanoacetate distilled at 144.6°/3 mm. yield: 10.8g; 67.5%) n_D^{20} 1.4768. (Found: C, 69.5; H 9.4. C₁₁H₂₁O₂N requires C, 69.9; H, 9.5%). A glassy residue remained in the distillation flask which did not solidify even on keeping in vacuum for a long period and this was considered to be a dimer.

The above ester (4 g) was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (100 ml.; 20%) for 20 hours; after removing the alcohol, the residue was acidified with cold hydrochloric acid when a solid was deposited which was filtered, washed, dried and had m.p. 118-28°. Pure cyclo-octyl malonic acid was crystallised from ethyl acetate in colourless needles, and melted at 135° with decomposition (*Lit.* m.p. 123-4°). (Yield: 1.5 g., 42%). (Found: C, 61.7; H, 8.5. C₁₁H₁₈O₄ requires C, 61.7; H, 8.5%).

Its *S*-benzyl isothiuronium salt was crystallised from hot water in colourless needles and had m.p. 116°.

Cyclo-octyl acetic acid: (A) Cyclo-octyl malonic acid (2.5 g) was heated in a tube in an oil bath at 135-140° for an hour and the dark oil was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried and ether recovered. The residue on distillation gave pure cyclo-octyl acetic acid as a colourless oil, b.p. 139-140°/2 mm. (Yield: 0.8 g; 40%) n_D^{20} 1.4762.

(B) Cyclo-octan-1-one-2-acetic acid (1 g) was dissolved in toluene (2 ml.) and refluxed with amalgamated zinc (5 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml) for one hundred hours on a sand bath; fresh quantities of hydrochloric acid (2 ml.) being added every six hours. The reaction product was worked up in the customary manner and pure cyclo-octyl acetic acid had b.p. 138-140°/2 mm. (*Lit.* b.p. 128-9°/0.5 mm.) (Yield: 0.5 g; 55%).

Its amide on crystallisation from dilute ethanol in colourless needles had m.p. 134°. (*Lit.* m.p. 130-2°).

Cyclo-octyl- α -methylacetic acid: (A) To sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (0.46 g; 0.02 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) contained in a flask fitted with a double walled reflux condenser carrying a guard tube, was added ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyanoacetate (4.46 g; 0.02 mol) in small lots with shaking. The contents were cooled in an ice bath, methyl iodide (4 ml) added, kept overnight and refluxed on a water bath until neutral (16 hours). The deposited oil was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed, dried, ether recovered and the residue distilled at 134.7°/2.8 mm. Pure *ethylcyclo octyl- α -cyano- α -methyl acetate* was redistilled at 137.8°/3 mm. as a colourless oil. (Yield: 2.8 g.; 50%). n_D^{25} 1.4732. (Found: C, 70.6; H, 9.5. $C_{14}H_{23}O_2N$ requires C, 70.8; H, 9.8%).

The above ester (2.5 g) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 ml.) for 60 hours; the reaction mixture was cooled, extracted with ether, ethereal solution washed, dried and ether recovered. The residue was later refluxed with alcoholic potash (100 ml.; 20%) for 20 hours; after removing the alcohol, the product was acidified with ice-cold hydrochloric acid and the deposited oil extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed, dried, ether recovered and the residue on distillation gave pure *cyclo-octyl- α -methyl acetic acid* as a colourless oil, b.p. 140.1°/4 mm. (Yield: 1 g; 43%). n_D^{25} 1.4765. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 11.60. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 71.7; H, 10.9%).

Its *S*-benzyl isothiuronium salt was crystallised from hot water in colourless plate m.p. 150°.

(B) Cyclo-octan-1-one- α -methyl 2-acetic acid (1 g.) was dissolved in toluene and refluxed with amalgamated zinc (5 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml) on a sand bath for 120 hrs; fresh quantities of conc. hydrochloric acid (2 ml.) was added every six hours. The reaction product was worked up in the usual manner and pure *cyclo-octane- α -methyl acetic acid* was obtained at 132°/1 mm. (Yield: 0.6 g, 63%).

Its *S*-benzylisothiuronium salt had m.p. 150°.

Cyclo-octyl- α -ethyl acetic acid: Ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyanoacetate (4.46 g; 0.02 mol.) was added in small lots with shaking to a cold solution of sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (0.46 g; 0.02 mol.) and absolute alcohol (30 ml.). Ethyl bromide (5 ml.) was added and the reaction mixture after keeping overnight at room temperature, was refluxed until neutral (20 hours). The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual manner and distilled; the first fraction collected upto 120°/1.6 mm. was rejected; the second fraction b.p. 121-142°/1.6 mm. was retreated with ethyl iodide and worked up in the usual manner. Pure *ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyano- α -ethylacetate* boiled at 143.4°/1.6 mm. (Yield: 2.7 g; 54%). n_D^{25} 1.4761. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 9.9. $C_{15}H_{25}O_2N$ requires C, 71.7; H, 10.0%).

The above ester (2 g.) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 ml.) for 60 hours; the reaction mixture was cooled, the organic material extracted with ether, ethereal solution washed, dried and ether recovered. The residue was again refluxed with alcoholic potash (50 ml.; 20%) for 20 hours; after removing the alcohol, the reaction product was acidified with ice-cold hydrochloric acid and the deposited oil extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed, dried, ether removed and the residue distilled when pure *cyclo-octyl- α -ethyl acetic acid* b.p. 160.2°/1 mm. was obtained as colourless oil. (Yield: 0.4 g.; 30%). (Found: C, 72.3; H, 11.1. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 72.7; H, 11.2%).

Its *S*-benzyl isothiuronium salt crystallised from hot water in colourless needles had m.p. 131°.

Cyclo-octyl- α -allyl acetic acid.—To sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (0.46 g.; 0.02 ml.) in absolute ethanol (30 ml.) was added ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyanoacetate (4.46 g.; 0.02 ml.) with continuous shaking and cooling; allyl bromide (3 g.; 0.02 mol.) was added, the reaction mixture, after keeping overnight at room temperature was refluxed on a water bath until neutral (16 hrs.). The resulting product was worked up as usual and pure ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyano- α -allyl acetate had b.p. 148-150°/0.5 mm. (Yield: 2.4 g.; 45%), n_D^{20} 1.4905. (Found: C, 73.3; H, 9.5. $C_{17}H_{23}O_2N$ requires C, 73.0; H, 9.6%).

The above ester (2.4 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (15 ml.); the solution after keeping overnight at room temperature was diluted with water until the solution became slightly turbid and refluxed on a sand bath first gently at a low flame for an hour and then strongly for eight hours. The reaction product which became dark was extracted with ether and worked up in the customary manner; ether was stripped off and the residue on distillation gave pure cyclo-octyl- α -allyl acetic acid as a colourless oil b.p. 147-9°/1 mm. (Yield: 0.9 g.; 33%) n_D^{21} 1.4975. (Found: C, 74.3; H, 10.6. $C_{15}H_{21}O_2$ requires C, 74.2; H, 10.5%).

Its *S*-benzyl isothiuronium salt was crystallised from hot water and had m.p. 117°.

Cyclo-octyl- α -benzyl acetic acid: To molecular sodium prepared from sodium (0.46 g., 0.02 mol.) in dry benzene (28 ml.), ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyanoacetate (4.46 g.; 0.02 mol.) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed until the evolution of hydrogen ceased (3 hrs.); benzyl chloride (2.5 g.; 0.02 mol.) was then added in small lots with continuous shaking. The reaction mixture, after keeping overnight at room temperature was refluxed on a water bath until neutral (20 hrs.). The benzene layer was separated, the aqueous layer extracted twice with benzene and the combined benzene extracts were washed with water, dried and benzene recovered. The residue on distillation gave pure ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyano- α -benzylacetate b.p. 178-180°/4 mm. as a colourless oil. (Yield: 2.2 g.; 35%) n_D^{21} 1.6238. (Found: C, 76.3; H, 8.6. $C_{20}H_{27}O_2N$ requires C, 76.6; H, 8.7%).

The above ester (2 g.) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml.) on a sand bath for 60 hours, the organic product extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried and ether recovered. The residue was further refluxed with alcoholic potash (40 ml; 20%) for 20 hours, alcohol recovered and the residue acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The deposited oil was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution worked up in the customary manner, and the residue on distillation gave pure cyclo-octyl benzyl acetic acid b.p. 196°/2 mm. (Yield: 0.4 g.; 20%). (Found: C, 78.4; H, 9.1. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.4; H, 9.3%).

Its *S*-benzylisothiuronium salt crystallised from hot water in colourless needles had m.p. 117°.

Cyclo-octyl succinic acid: To sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (0.46 g.; 0.02 mol) and absolute ethanol (30 ml.) was added ethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyanoacetate (4.46g.; 0.02 mol) in small lots with shaking. Ethyl bromoacetate (3.4 g.; 0.02 mol.) was then added to the cooled mixture and the contents after keeping overnight at room temperature were refluxed on a water bath until neutral (24 hours). On the completion of the reaction, water

was added and the deposited oil extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed, dried and ether recovered. The residue on distillation gave pure *diethyl cyclo-octyl- α -cyano-succinate* at 172.4°/3 mm. and 186.8°/5 mm. (Yield: 2.8 g.; 45%). (Found: C, 66.00; H, 8.7. C₁₇H₂₇O₄N requires C, 66.00; H, 8.8%).

A mixture of the above ester (2.6 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml.) was refluxed on a sand bath for 120 hours; additional quantities of the acid (2 ml.) were added after every 6 hours. The semi-solid product was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed twice with water and then with aqueous sodium carbonate (10%). The combined alkaline extracts on acidification with hydrochloric acid deposited a colourless solid, m.p. 118-121°, pure *cyclo-octyl succinic acid* was crystallised from anhydrous benzene in colourless cubes, m.p. 127.5° (Yield: 0.8 g.; 28%). (Found: C, 62.8; H, 8.6. C₁₁H₂₀O₄ requires C, 63.1; H, 8.8%).

Its *p-toluidide* was crystallised from dilute ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 147°.

Cyclo-octyl succinic acid anhydride was prepared by refluxing the acid (2.3 g.; 0.01 mol) with acetic anhydride (7 ml.) on a sand bath for 4 hours. After removing excess of acetic anhydride under reduced pressure, the residue on distillation gave pure anhydride at 150°/1 mm. (Yield: 1.0 g.; 80%) n_D^{27} 1.4915. This was characterised by the preparation of the following derivatives:

(a) *anilic acid* m.p. 161°, (b) *p-toluidinic acid* m.p. 153°, (c) *m-toluidinic acid*, m.p. 141°, (d) *o-toluidinic acid* m.p. 143°, (e) *p-anisidinic acid* m.p. 109°, (f) *p-phenetidinic acid* m.p. 135-8°, (g) *p-bromoanilic acid* m.p. 166° and (h) β -*naphthylinic acid* m.p. 174°.

Resolution of dl-cyclo-octyl succinic acid: Cyclo-octyl succinic acid (4.5 g.; 0.02 mol.) was mixed with brucine (17.2 g.; 0.04 mol.) and the mixture dissolved in boiling water (350 ml.) The solution was filtered hot, allowed to cool and kept at room temperature for 24 hours when 15 gms. of the salt was deposited. In the table below is given the volume of the solvent (water) at each subsequent crystallisation and the weight of the salt recrystallised.

Crystallisation	Wt. of the salt (grams)	Volume of the solvent (ml.)
I	15.0	250
II	8.4	140
III	5.6	100
IV	5.0	100

The brucine salt (4.6 g.) obtained after the fourth crystallisation was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid and the acid was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried and after removing the solvent a solid (0.7 g.) was obtained which had a rotation (α)_D²⁷ 20° ($l = \frac{1}{2}$; C, 0.9; $\alpha = 0.09^\circ$) in ethanol. On further purification and acid of maximum rotation (α)_D²⁷ 29.3° ($l = \frac{1}{2}$; C = 0.7615; $\alpha = 0.11^\circ$) was obtained.

Isolation of the laevo-isomer: The parent mother liquor and mother liquors from I, II and III crystallisations were combined together and concentrated in vacuum to half its bulk (420 ml.). The concentrate was cooled at 0° and the solid separated by filtration. This process was repeated twice and the resulting mother liquor was decomposed with dilute

hydrochloric acid and the acid extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried and ether recovered; the residue had rotation ($[\alpha]_D^{27}$) -17.5° ($l=1$; $C=0.8$; $[\alpha]=0.07^\circ$) in alcohol. The active acid on further purification with biucine and recrystallisation from benzene had ($[\alpha]_D^{27}$) -28.2° ($l=1$; $C=0.9921$; $[\alpha]=0.14^\circ$) in alcohol. Both the isomeric acids had m.p. 119° .

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